

MODERN INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO THE FORMATION OF COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In primary school, communicative competence is of particular importance. At primary school age, internal speech, monologue speech is finally formed, the foundations of written speech are laid. The formation of communicative competence in primary school is a condition for the success of teaching younger students.*

It is important to begin the formation of communicative skills at primary school age for gradual development in the future. Activation of the communicative activity of younger schoolchildren involves the process of encouraging students to energetic, purposeful communication. Communication is an integral part of any lesson, therefore, the formation of students' communicative skills leads to an improvement in the quality of the educational process.

Keywords: *formation, innovation, communication skills, pedagogy, psychology, mathematics, teaching methods, primary education, training.*

СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ ИННОВАЦИОННЫЙ ПОДХОД К ФОРМИРОВАНИЮ КОММУНИКАТИВНЫХ НАВЫКОВ У УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССОВ

Аннотация. *В начальной школе особую значимость приобретает коммуникативная компетенция. В младшем школьном возрасте окончательно формируется внутренняя речь, монологическая речь, закладываются основы письменной речи. Формирование коммуникативной компетенции в начальной школе является условием успешности обучения младших школьников.*

Важно начать формирование коммуникативных умений именно в младшем школьном возрасте для поэтапного развития в дальнейшем. Активизация коммуникативной деятельности младших школьников предполагает процесс побуждения учащихся к энергичному, целенаправленному общению. Общение - неотъемлемая часть любого урока, поэтому формирование коммуникативных умений учащихся ведет к повышению качества учебно - воспитательного процесса.

Ключевые слова: *формирования, инновация, коммуникативных навыков, педагогика, психология, математика, методика преподавания, начального образования, обучения.*

INTRODUCTION

From birth, a child enters a world where he is surrounded by people who communicate with each other, interact and build relationships. At preschool age, there is a process of mastering primary communication skills in order to learn to understand this world, to be able to interact with people in the process of communication.

Already upon entering school, a child comes with his baggage of communication skills and they are not always enough to safely join the team of peers and start interacting with them.

There are constant changes in the demands among society, thereby expanding the possibilities of communication, and increasing the importance of communication skills in the context of school education. There is an increasing need to use various forms of education in the process of education, which contribute to the formation of students' ability to work together: to

cooperate, exchange ideas, accept criticism and understand the fact that there may be many ways to solve the problems that have arisen [4, p. 137].

One of the requirements of the standard at the stage of primary general education is the development of skills of cooperation with adults and peers in various social situations, taking into account the position of other people, the ability not to create conflicts and find ways out of controversial situations, the ability to listen and engage in dialogue [2].

Due to the fact that interpersonal communication skills are not sufficiently developed at primary school age, there are many difficulties due to which a child may withdraw into himself, feel lonely, or use unsuccessful ways to build friendly relationships with peers. Gradually, communicative difficulties arise in relation to teachers, parents, peers, which will later be expressed in the child in the form of aggressiveness, negativism, disobedience, self-doubt, and a decrease in self-esteem. The younger student will have dissatisfaction with his position in the team, which can also make a negative contribution to the moral development of the individual.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The development of communication skills takes place within the framework of the age characteristics of students and the cognitive sphere of the child. Their development in primary school age plays a special role. This is the reason for the urgency of considering this issue today.

The situation of modern school education requires students to the active solution of complex communicative tasks, such as the whole human life consists of interaction with society, building relationships with various people through communication. Communication itself plays a very important role for any person and his mental state, which is reflected in his behavior towards other people.

Researchers L. S. Vygotsky, V. N. Myasishchev, V. Stern, K. Buhler point to the close relationship of communication and mental processes. They define communication as a mechanism for the development of people's relationships, the form of existence of these relationships and the way of existence of the most important aspects of the mental world of an individual [19].

In the process of communication, each person gradually acquires communication skills. There are many different approaches and views to the definition of "communication skills". To date, there is no unambiguous interpretation of this concept.

Platonov K.K. gives the following definition of the concept: a skill action that is carried out by a person without the participation of consciousness, that is, automatically, due to the fact that a person has carried out this action many times in the past [11, p. 11].

Also, the skill is considered as "an action that has reached the level of automatism and is characterized by integrity, the absence of element-by-element consciousness" [23, p. 18], "an action brought to automatism in the process of repetitions" [9].

A skill is not always considered as an action. Many researchers have a different point of view on this definition. For example, researcher Yu.O. Petrov said that a skill is not an automated action. Action is primarily a process, and skill is a characteristic of the process and its quality [20].

Speaking about communication skills, they mean automated communicative components of speech activity, the formation of which is facilitated by the example of adults, communication with peers, teachers and parents.

The concept of "communication skills" is also understood as the communicative actions of students, the ability to correctly apply them in the process of communication and to build their behavior in accordance with the tasks of communication.

In psychology, "communication skills" is a characteristic of the peculiarities of a person's orientation in communication processes, reflecting the degree of adequacy of their understanding of the main dominants of the communicator [23].

Zaitseva K.P. considers communication skills from several positions [25]:

1. Communication as interaction (communicative actions aimed at determining the interlocutor's position and the ability to accept it for the implementation of tasks);

2. Communication as cooperation (search for a common opinion for work efficiency and achieving the best result);

3. Communicative and speech actions (act as a means of transmitting information to people around them)

At primary school age, you can develop such interpersonal communication skills as:

- taking into account different points of view on the same question, focusing on the position of the interlocutor when interacting with him;

- the use of speech tools to perform communicative tasks, possession of monologue speech;

- the ability to accept different opinions and strives to use different positions of interlocutors in cooperation with them;

- have your own opinion and position on any questions;

- when disagreements arise, come to a common solution to the issue, develop the ability to negotiate with each other;

- it is correct to ask questions;

- use speech to regulate their actions [25, p. 19].

The formed communicative skills are considered as the ability of younger schoolchildren to analyze linguistic and non-linguistic concepts, phenomena, patterns, compare, generalize them, highlight the main and secondary signs; to present and describe objects, phenomena, events using linguistic expressive means, make assumptions about the way to solve problem situations, select evidence to confirm or refute their own and others' opinions, positions, use their own and indirect experience and critically evaluate their own and others' statements [6].

With a low level of formation of communicative skills in younger schoolchildren, there is an inability to use communicative means to build interpersonal relationships in the class team, minimal ability to use the language system.

The average level of formation of communicative skills indicates the presence of initial skills in using the language system, partial mastery of communicative means.

RESULTS

The high level of development of interpersonal communication skills indicates the high abilities of the younger student to use communicative means of communication and creative application of socio-cultural, dialectical information in communicative situations [24].

Speaking about communication skills, E. I. Ayupova points to three functions of communication:

1. Cognitive – transmitting, receiving the emotional and intellectual content of the message, using non-verbal and verbal means of communication, understanding the partner;

2. Affective – organization of various forms of joint activity;
3. Regulatory – management of communication participants.

The communication process plays a major role in mastering communication skills. It is during communication that a person acquires the ability to find a way out of various controversial situations, establish contacts with people around him, correctly interpret their behavior and calmly respond to various manifestations of emotions, perceive criticism and learn to correctly express their disagreement with something, dissatisfaction and other feelings of rejection, the ability to start and conduct a conversation, keep interest the interlocutor in communication.

Normally, the formation of a younger student's personality, as noted by I. P. Podlasy, occurs under the influence of new relationships with adults and peers, new types of activities and communication, inclusion in the whole system of collectives. It is at this age that the child develops elements of social feelings, and develops skills of social behavior (collectivism, responsibility for one's own actions, camaraderie, mutual assistance, etc.) [25].

It is possible to identify the features that characterize this "crisis":

- the child comprehends his experiences, which contributes to a new attitude towards himself;
- there is a logical generalization of one's own feelings;
- loss of your spontaneity;

Changes in the social situation of development in connection with admission to school is the main factor that most significantly determines the development of a younger student. Starting training, a junior student is faced with work in a team, which will be evaluated by others with a socially significant assessment.

A child enrolled in primary school acquires not only a new social circle, but also new additional responsibilities related to educational activities. The surrounding adults communicate with the child already as a person who has responsibilities to study and has some responsibility for their actions [19]. Society begins to make demands to the student that he has not met before.

Communicative development follows different lines. These are quantitative accumulation (increase in vocabulary, volume of utterance) and qualitative changes (pronunciation, development of coherent speech, understanding of reversed speech). However, the main criterion for the intensity and success of communicative personality formation is the ability to understand, set and solve various communicative tasks, i.e. the ability to correctly and optimally use one's speech-thinking activity in communication with other people, the media and with oneself.

The introduction of a set of specially organized exercises in literary reading lessons contributes to obtaining stable positive results. The situation of modern school education requires the student to actively solve new complex communicative tasks: organizing business communication of students with each other and with the teacher about the material being studied. Therefore, it is very important to develop high forms of communication with adults and peers in a child, which is a prerequisite for the formation of a new type of relationship between teacher and student, between classmates. Dialogue, live communication, trainings, language communication are the foundation on which schoolchildren will grow and develop.

The implementation of these functions is directly related to how fluently a person speaks. The gift of the word," wrote L. Uspensky. To develop this "gift" so that the child's language is "slurred" as little as possible, to make sure that his thoughts "do not jump out disheveled and

half-dressed", to teach him to enjoy the beauty of the spoken and written word, to feel its true meaning, is necessary in our time.

The structure of communicative universal learning activities contains the following elements:

1. Cognitive element, the essence of which is the presentation by primary school students of all kinds of communication: direct and indirect, oral and written, verbal and non-verbal, in native and foreign languages.

2. The axiological element contains motives and goals, which include: request and exchange of information, presentation, persuasion and rejection, emotional self-expression.

3. The interactive element represents universal and substantive communicative actions, and along with this various means of communication: monologue, dialogue, statement, message, discussion, question, dispute, argumentation, refusal, telephone conversation, letter.

4. The empirical element includes reflection, followed by correction of methods and evaluation of the achievements of the communication process [4].

The communicative method provides opportunities for cooperation by developing the following skills:

–to hear and understand your partner, plan and coordinate joint actions, share roles, control joint actions, be able to negotiate/discuss, express your thoughts correctly, respect your partner and yourself in the communication process;

–take into account different points of view and strive to coordinate them;

–have your own opinion and point of view, be able to agree, make a common decision when working together.

Of all the skills related to the communication sphere, there are two, especially important for students:

1) Communication and interaction, consisting in the ability to transmit this or that information both in writing and orally, through the use of means of speech to discuss and argue one's position;

2) Group/collective work involves the ability to create working contacts, productive cooperation and assistance in joint activities [8].

According to the developers of the Standards, the level of formation of communicative skills in most children does not correspond to age characteristics, which creates a number of problems in the personal development of schoolchildren. That is why, in the process of forming the communicative culture of the student's personality, the teacher should pay special attention to the implementation of a set of psychocorrective and developmental measures in working with younger schoolchildren.

Thus, the creation of real conditions at school for overcoming the egocentric position, the successful formation of skills of productive interaction with peers will serve as a significant means of countering numerous personality disorders in children [12].

DISCUSSION

Along with this, the younger school age is especially successful for the formation of communicative competence. A child at this age is particularly sensitive to language phenomena, he may notice an interest in understanding his experience, both related to speech and communication in general. Researchers have identified primary school age as the best period for the development of communicative universal learning activities. In this age period, social

behavior, acquisition of skills and mastery of the art of communication between children are especially effective [10].

A.G. Samokhvalova focuses on the following neoplasms of a junior schoolboy in a communicative environment [15]:

- the qualitative level of development of relaxed regulation of communicative behavior;
- internal planning of communicative actions followed by introspection;
- creating motives for self-improvement in the field of communication;
- willingness to master various communication techniques;
- focus on productive interaction with peers.

A.G. Asmolov notes three main aspects

of communicative activity that characterize the general level of communication development in younger schoolchildren [6]:

1. Communication as interaction. In this case, the communicative actions are focused on taking into account the position of the interlocutor / partner in the activity. It is important to accept someone else's point of view, getting rid of the unconscious attribution and imposition of one's point of view on other people, i.e. overcoming the egocentric position in interpersonal and spatial relationships, so that the student begins to better understand other people's thoughts and feelings;

2. Communication as cooperation. An important component of the communicative method is the coordination of efforts to achieve a common goal, organization and implementation of joint actions, such as: distribution of initial actions and operations, exchange of methods of action, mutual understanding, planning of common ways of working and reflection. Here, students need to be able not just to express their own opinion, but also to be able to convince others, to give in, to maintain a friendly attitude towards each other during disputes and conflicts, to take the initiative, that is, to work not only individually, but also to pay attention to the partner in the activity;

3. Communication as an interpretation. The communication and speech activity acts as a means of transmitting information to other people. the formation of reflection. Children's speech, which is in the early stages of development, is a means of communication that is always directed at someone, at the same time developing as an increasingly accurate way of displaying the content of the subject and the process of the child's activity itself. Thus, the individual awareness and reflection of the child are born in interaction and cooperation with other people.

Researchers identify three factors that create a completely new position of an elementary school student in the communication space: the acquisition of new social roles; a sufficient level of development of reflexive skills; the presentation of requirements regarding the development of speech [19].

If we consider the first factor in more detail, it becomes obvious that the student is constantly responsible for educational activities not only at school, but also in the family. A child of primary school age is considered not only as a unique person, but also as a person who has assumed the responsibility to engage in education. The ability to make reflection is most vividly formed in elementary school. The child has a process of adaptation to standard conditions, where he masters mental actions, masters the content of the leading forms of human consciousness (science, art, morality), learns to follow the traditions and social expectations of society [11].

At the same time, according to I.P.Podlasov, educational activity creates new conditions for the personal development of a younger student, while putting forward requirements for the development of speech, attention, memory, thinking and imagination [21]. Of particular importance is the development of speech, which should be distinguished by literacy of expression and clarity of thinking.

Thus, the child assumes responsibility for his speech, which is an integral component for establishing contact with other people. J. Piaget in his works considers the concept of "social speech" as speech addressed to listeners, whose task is to influence others, to encourage them to act.

As an opposite, egocentric speech is presented, which the child pronounces for himself, about himself. J. Piaget designated long conversations of the child with himself, despite the presence of other interlocutors nearby, as a "collective monologue". He believed that the process of forming a child's communication skills contains "a gradual transition from egocentric speech with its characteristic collective monologue to socialized speech that connects children in the process of their communication" [22].

L.V. Vygotsky, continuing to study this issue, came to the conclusion that by switching to social speech, egocentric speech does not disappear, but "connects with thought", passing into internal speech. In the process of combining thinking and speech, the child, trying to control his actions, uses silent inner speech when solving social problems of a behavioral nature, in which he needs an appropriate solution [14]. Thus, internal speech plays a key role in the development of communication.

It allows the child to exert the desired influence on the interlocutor, which, according to A.N. Leontiev, becomes the main goal of communication [19].

L.I. Bozhovich notes that at this stage of development children acquire collective connections, public opinions and mutual assessments begin to form. The basis on which children's relationships are laid is gradually becoming an educational activity.

"The main need for communication is the desire to cooperate with comrades, which does not depend on a particular situation. Gradually, the image of a peer is formed, thereby friendship is born. Based on this, there is a subjective approach to other children, that is, the ability to see them as an equal person, take into account their interests and willingness to help them" [10].

Thus, the main task of the teacher becomes the upbringing of a well-rounded, educated and communication-competent personality.

Communicative competence does not arise from scratch, it is formed. Like any other competence, it cannot be formed outside of activity. The basis of its formation is the experience of human communication. The teacher forms this type of competence by setting the standard of communicative skills by his own communication, organizing the interaction of students with each other. To this end, I pay great attention to one of the ways of collective mutual learning - working in pairs. Starting to organize the communication of children in pairs, I conduct trainings on developing the skills they need for pair work.

These include:

- the ability to listen to your partner and hear what he says;
- working in constant noise;
- search for the necessary information;
- use of individual accounting sheets;

- the ability to translate an image into words and words into an image.

This work makes the lessons interesting, lively, unlike each other.

Of the forms of work that stimulate the improvement of students' communicative competence in the lessons of the surrounding world, the following can be named:

- conducting a correspondence tour of exhibition halls, museums, streets and squares of cities around the world (a role-playing game where one or more students perform the duties of a guide, and others - tourists),
- oral or written invitation to the exhibition, dialogue in the exhibition hall "At the picture ...",
- preparation of questions for interviews with the artist, writer, director, actor.

These exercises develop students' ability to correlate the content and form of statements with the speech situation, discipline thinking, sharpen the sense of language, teach them to use it flexibly, have great educational value, as they increase speech culture and the culture of behavior in general.

The whole classroom turns into a science station. There is an independent research work of students. Children are divided into groups: geographers, botanists, ecologists, zoologists. Each group has a specific task, which is set out in the cards. They defend their mini-studies at the end of the lesson. In the process of such tasks, we develop cognitive interest, teach them to choose the main thing from the general material and bring it into the system.

Working in pairs and groups helps to organize communication, because every child has the opportunity to talk with an interested interlocutor. One of the main organizations of dialogue is the creation of an atmosphere of trust and goodwill, freedom and mutual understanding, co-creation of equals and different. Children's participation in games and exercises ensures the emergence of friendly relations between children, and group support causes a sense of security, and even the most timid and anxious children overcome fear.

In mathematics classes, the development of communicative competence involves the use of various collective techniques: group work, discussion, didactic games and others. For example, when studying the topic "Problem Solving" in 3rd grade, the class is divided into several groups. Each group receives its own task, where the algorithm for solving the problem given by the same condition is specified. The results of each group's work are shown on the board. After that, a stage of discussion of the methods used to solve the problem is organized, suggestions are made, the advantages and disadvantages of each method are evaluated, and a conclusion is made. As a result of the application of this form of organization of activity, students acquire the skills of working in a group, master the ways of interacting with people around them. They develop the ability to ask questions, to listen to the other. Develops a "sense of elbow", the ability to work not side by side, but together, attention to others.

I believe that such techniques contribute to the improvement of the educational and cognitive process in children, the formation of their skills to independently set goals, perform educational actions, monitor the progress of educational actions and evaluate the result of their activities.

These exercises develop students' ability to correlate the content and form of statements with the speech situation, discipline thinking, sharpen the sense of language, teach them to use it flexibly, have great educational value, as they increase speech culture and the culture of behavior in general.

Any excursion involves a large amount of information, students learn the ability to listen, hear, perceive and process information: after the excursions, children share their impressions orally, write reviews, travel notes.

The use of computer technologies in the lessons of the surrounding world allows students to form and develop such key competencies as educational, cognitive, informational, communicative, and general cultural.

The guys prepare their messages for the lessons (select the material, highlight the main thing, tell classmates in the lesson, show photos, paintings, think through questions, etc.)

In technology lessons, children often perform group types of work: compositions, crafts made of various materials. Such work requires students to be able to negotiate, discuss, listen, justify, etc.

Extracurricular activities are of great importance for the development of communication skills of younger schoolchildren. It expands the scope of the school curriculum, forms curiosity, increases the erudition of schoolchildren, creates a situation of success for all students, both strong and weak. The types of extracurricular activities I have used are different: quizzes, contests, themed class hours, holidays. When preparing these events, I try to use the method of creative projects: in grades 1 – 2 I compose myself or involve parents, in grades 3 – 4 students learn to perform independently, and I only direct. Creative groups are formed depending on the type of activity: artistic, dance, vocal, artists.

CONCLUSIONS

Analyzing the psychological and pedagogical literature, we found that communicative universal actions involve the formed ability to listen and tactfully conduct a dialogue with various people, owning monological and dialogical forms of speech, taking into account the position of other people, taking part in a collective discussion of the problem, joining groups, building productive interaction with peers and adults, the ability to avoid conflicts. The primary school age is the most effective period for the formation of communicative universal educational, which is explained by age characteristics.

Thus, the younger school age is favorable for building relationships. It is at this age that communication with adults and peers within the framework of educational and extracurricular activities contributes to the formation of the nature of the interaction of the younger student with the people around him. Communication becomes more conscious and versatile. Children learn to establish friendships and acquire various skills of interaction with each other.

In this regard, there is a need to control the formation and lack of formation of communicative skills that contribute to the successful implementation of the educational and cognitive process and the ability of students to manage their behavior, use the most rational ways of action in solving communicative tasks.

Also, the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature on the topic showed that communication skills are the ability of a person to interact with other people, adequately interpreting the information received, as well as correctly transmitting it.

During the pedagogical experiment, an extracurricular pedagogical project was developed and implemented, aimed at the formation of communicative universal educational actions of younger schoolchildren through the creation of the following pedagogical conditions:

- to develop a pedagogical project for teaching children to design;

- this project will be developed and implemented taking into account the age-related psychological and physiological characteristics of primary school age;
- to give students the opportunity to choose the topic and ways of implementing the project, independently distribute the work among the members of the group;
- to implement the project, use active methods of organizing cooperation of working group participants, such as: "Brainstorming" (A.Osborne), "Zigzag" (Johnson and Holubek), Jigsaw Puzzle.

As a result, the work carried out on the formation of communicative 4th grade students through project activities on the proposed conditions turned out to be effective.

At the initial stage of the study, incoming diagnostics showed that the percentage of students with a high level of communicative development was very low. After the introduction of exercises on the formation of communicative competencies in the lessons of literary reading and the Russian language, the number of students with a high level of communicative development has become significantly higher, and accordingly the indicator with a low level of communicative development has decreased.

The selected set of exercises and methodical games contributes to the achievement of positive results in the formation of communicative skills of younger schoolchildren.

The percentage of students, winners of school competitions of various levels has significantly increased. They are active participants in school-wide holidays.

Thus, the effectiveness of activities to ensure the positive dynamics of the level of formation of communicative competencies of students in primary school is optimal. Based on this, we can conclude about the prospects of further work on the formation of communicative competencies of younger schoolchildren.

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